

Editorial

Earth Observation for Ecosystems Monitoring in Space and Time: A Special Issue in Remote Sensing

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Abstract: This Editorial introduces the papers published in the special issue “Earth Observation for Ecosystems Monitoring in Space and Time” which includes the most important researchers in the field and the most challenging aspects of the application of remote sensing to study ecosystems.

Keywords: forests; marine ecosystems; modeling techniques; remote sensing; terrestrial ecosystems

1. Introduction: Why a Special Issue on Earth Observation for Ecosystems Monitoring in Space and Time?

Nowadays, a number of different sensors are available for studying ecosystems from space. This allows researchers to study ecosystems at a number of spatial scales (considering both grain and extent) with a high temporal resolution.

Further, ecological theory has been applied to remote sensing data to monitor species dispersal and diversity over space and time. Ecosystem-based models have also been developed to monitor, at a high temporal resolution, Earth surface changes over large areas. The need for high temporal resolution for studying global and local changes is directly related to the use of techniques other than field-based monitoring. Consequently, remote sensing is critical for ecosystems monitoring.

Remote sensing and ecosystems monitoring challenges include (i) scale issues, (ii) data gathering and analysis, and (iii) software development.

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Conflicts of Interest

The author declares no conflict of interest.

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